

SOCIAL FACTORS FORMING DEVIANT BEHAVIOR ON THE BASIS OF THE THEORY OF SOCIAL CONTROL STAGMATIZATION

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Annotation: In psychology, factors influencing the formation of deviant behavior in individuals are interpreted differently according to various theories. In some theories, biological factors play an important role in the formation of deviant behavior, while in others the role of social factors is highly appreciated. Still other theories recognize the role of psychological factors as the primary factor in the formation of deviant behavior. In this paragraph, the factors influencing the formation of deviant behavior are scientifically considered.

Keywords: deviant behavior, delinquent behavior, socio-psychological analysis, personality, society, deviation, norm.

Annotatsiya: Psixologiyada shaxslarda deviant xulq-atvor shakllanishiga ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi omillar turli nazariyalarda har xil talqin etiladi. Ayrim nazariyalarda deviant xulq-atvor shakllanishida biologik omillar muhim ahamiyat kasb etsa, ayrimlarida ijtimoiy omillarning o'rni yuqori baholanadi. Yana boshqa nazariyalar esa deviant xulq-atvor shakllanishida psixologik omillarning rolini birlamchi omil sifatida e'tirof etadi. Ushbu paragrafda deviant xulq-atvor shakllanishiga ta'sir etuvchi omillar ilmiy jihatdan ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: deviant xulq-atvor, delinkvent xulq-atvor, ijtimoiy-psixologik tahlil, shaxs, jamiyat, og'ish, norma.

Abstract: In psychology, the factors influencing the formation of deviant behavior in individuals are interpreted differently across various theories. Some theories emphasize the importance of biological factors in the formation of deviant behavior, while others place a high value on the role of social factors. Still

other theories recognize psychological factors as the primary determinants in the formation of deviant behavior. In this paragraph, the factors influencing the formation of deviant behavior are examined from a scientific perspective.

Key words: deviant behavior, delinquent behavior, socio-psychological analysis, personality, society, deviation, norm.

Аннотация: В психологии факторы, влияющие на формирование девиантного поведения у индивидов, по-разному интерпретируются в различных теориях. Некоторые теории подчеркивают важность биологических факторов в формировании девиантного поведения, тогда как другие высоко оценивают роль социальных факторов. Третьи теории признают психологические факторы первостепенными в формировании девиантного поведения. В данном параграфе факторы, влияющие на формирование девиантного поведения, рассматриваются с научной точки зрения.

Ключевые слова: девиантное поведение, делинквентное поведение, социально-психологический анализ, личность, общество, девиантность, норма.

INTRODUCTION

Biological factors influencing the formation of deviant behavior include innate personality traits and hereditary-genetic characteristics. At the end of the 19th century, the Italian psychiatrist Cesare Lombroso put forward the theory of a direct connection between criminal behavior and the biological characteristics of a person. According to his theory, people are born criminals. The scientist attributes this to degeneration (decline in mental balance, mental stability, activity and working capacity) at the previous stages of human evolution. He emphasizes that this can be determined by 37 characteristic anthropometric signs.

The famous American physician and psychologist William G. Sheldon in the first half of the 20th century put forward the idea that behavioral and temperament

types are interconnected with the somatic structure of a person. The scientist emphasizes that people with ectomorph, mesomorph and endomorph structures have unique personality traits that differ from each other. Based on his research on human behavior, Sheldon concluded that mesomorph types (in Kretschmer's theory, people with an athletic body structure, heavy bones, a strong skeleton, broad shoulders and lower jaws) may be more prone to behavioral deviations, although they do not always become criminals. One of the scientists who conducted research on the genetic connection of deviant behavior is W. Pearce. According to the results of the scientist's research, the presence of an additional Y chromosome in men may determine a tendency to criminal behavior, in particular, aggression. Witkin and his colleagues paid attention to sex chromosome abnormalities in deviant behavior. Using the materials of the Danish crime study, it was found that among men with an XYY chromosome composition, the level of crime was higher than among individuals without additional chromosomes.

Other biological factors, such as hormone levels (especially testosterone), brain damage, organic brain diseases, nervous system characteristics, and neural network maturity, are also considered determinants of an individual's deviant behavior. Attempts have been made to find a link between deviant behavior and deviant behavior by recording the activity of the cerebral cortex and autonomic nervous system, conducting biochemical studies, and determining electrodermal and cardiovascular correlates in individuals who have committed crimes or have psychopathic traits and who are not sufficiently socialized. A. E. Lichko identifies the genetic factor, organic brain damage, acceleration and infantilism as the main biological factors influencing the formation of behavior in adolescents. Leading experts argue that the biological characteristics of a person do not in themselves cause crime, but rather affect the dynamics of behavior, which is the morphological and psychophysiological basis of human behavior. This fully applies to all forms of deviant behavior.

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE ON THE TOPIC

The influence of the external environment, namely unfavorable upbringing conditions, is of decisive importance on the social factors of the formation of deviant behavior. According to E.G. Dzugkoyeva [1, p. 22], L.K. Gayfullina [2, p. 16] and V.I. Trofimova [3, p. 16-24], behavior and its disorders in children are determined by biological and social factors.

However, G.V. Gribanova [4, p. 13-20], R.D. Triger [5, p. 7-14], D.I. Al-Rahhal [6, p. 17], A.O. Drobinskaya [7, p. 144], L.M. Shipit-synalar [8, p. 62-66] explains behavioral deviations in such children mainly by social factors, as the causes of such deviations are often related to the influence of family, school, and nearby groups. The lack of full and positive communication with parents is one of the important causes of deviant behavior and negative reactions in children. Due to the lack of emotional ties in the family, children have difficulty identifying the positive character traits of their parents, which forces the child to look for alternative models for acting in the external environment. Social factors play an important role in the formation of deviant behavior, since deviant behavior represents a set of behaviors that deviate from generally accepted norms and values in society. It can include crimes, violation of rules, aggressive behavior and other forms of negative behavior.

One of the main social factors influencing the formation of deviant behavior is the social environment, because if there are many people around a person who exhibit deviant behavior or if there is an unfavorable social environment, then the person is more likely to have an increased tendency to deviant behavior. For example, adolescents who grow up in problematic families that lack support and proper upbringing may be more prone to deviant behavior. Another important social factor is social instability, which is characterized by a lack of stability in society, social order and the unsatisfactory functioning of social institutions. Another social factor that influences the formation of deviant behavior is social inequality, because

when people feel that they live in an unjust society and are deprived of available opportunities, they may be inclined to choose alternative ways to achieve their goals, including deviant behavior. For example, individuals from lower social classes with limited educational and employment opportunities are more likely to be prone to crime and other forms of deviant behavior. Among the social factors that influence the formation of deviant behavior are also the factors that influence the formation of deviant behavior during the intensional, oral, anal, and oedipal stages of child development. Inability to form proper relationships by individuals can also be included. Factors such as insufficient affection from the mother for the child during these developmental periods, the death of the mother, the child's placement in an orphanage or another family, prolonged starvation during infancy, early discipline, as well as regular quarrels between spouses in the family, also have a significant impact on the formation of deviant behavior [9, p. 31-34].

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Philosophers often argue about whether aggression is an innate or conditioned trait. In particular, Jean-Jacques Rousseau sees the negative relations existing in society as the culprit in the manifestation of aggression in humans. Thomas Hobbes, on the other hand, considers aggression to be an innate trait and puts forward the idea that strict control is necessary to curb it. In the 21st century, the ideas that aggressive impulses are innate were supported in the field of psychology by Sigmund Freud and Konrad Lorenz. Z. Freud interpreted this as a process of directing the energy of the primitive death instinct in a person to external objects, while K. Lorenz considers aggression to be a form of adaptive behavior. According to the psychoanalytic approach, Z. Freud was the first to pay attention to this problem. He put forward a systematic theory of the psyche, explaining it through the dynamic interaction of the components of the "id", "ego" and "super-ego". "Id" is interpreted as the main source of human activity, determining the ontogenetic and phylogenetic development of the psyche. "Ego" is a component that controls the

unconscious inclinations of the “id” and prohibits socially unacceptable desires and wishes. “Super-ego” represents the consciousness of society and embodies the norms and ideals accepted in it. According to Z. Freud, the “ego” constantly strives to maintain a balance between the unconscious impulses of the “id” and the prohibitions of the “super-ego”. As a result, in the process of complex relationships between these three components, aggressive or deviant behavior occurs.

CONCLUSION

One of the social factors influencing the formation of deviant behavior is the social environment. If there are many deviant individuals in a person's environment or if there is an unfavorable social environment, then the probability of an individual's tendency to deviant behavior increases. For example, adolescents who do not have support and proper upbringing, growing up in conflicting families, may be more prone to deviant behavior. Another important social factor is social disorder, which is characterized by a lack of stability in society, unsatisfactory functioning of social order and institutions. Biological, social and psychological factors influence the formation of deviant behavior. In this process, biological factors include innate personality traits and hereditary-genetic factors, social factors include the influence of the external environment, that is, unfavorable upbringing conditions, and psychological factors include a sense of imperfection, frustration, behavioral identification, as well as the relationships that arise between the components of the psyche - id, ego and super ego.

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